

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS AS CORRELATES TO TEACHER'S PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR AN ACTION PLAN

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Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Correlates to Teacher's Performance: Basis for an Action Plan

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the instructional leadership of school administrators as correlate to teachers' performance which served as basis for an action plan during the school year 2024-2025. In terms of Resource Provider, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.46 which was verbally interpreted as Always. In terms of Instructional Resource, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.62 which was verbally interpreted as Always. In terms of Communicator, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.51 which was verbally interpreted as Always. In terms of Visible Leader, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.55 which was verbally interpreted as Always. The majority of 151 teacher-respondents or 63.58% at rank 1 have an Outstanding IPCRF performances. The table presented the results of the Teacher Performance Evaluation for the academic year 2023-2024, as assessed through the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). Teacher performance was categorized into two main ranges based on their evaluation scores. The highest category, ranging from 4.1 to 5.00, denoted "Outstanding" performance, with 96 teachers, accounting for 63.58% of the total evaluated, achieving scores within this range. The second category, spanning from 3.1 to 4.00, signified "Very Satisfactory" performance, with 55 teachers, comprising 36.42% of the total, falling into this range. A significant relationship between the instructional leadership roles of the school administrators and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF is evident.

Keywords: *communicator, instructional resource, resource provider*

Introduction

Education is undoubtedly a way to cure individuals' ignorance. Through it, individuals have the necessary skills, knowledge, and behavior to help them live modest lives. Therefore, education is one of the best instruments that contributes to humanity's effective development and progress in all aspects of life.

In the education sector, it is a great idea to note that there is someone who leads with passion and commitment. A person who leads constituents to hone their skills, develop their potential, and achieve common goals for the organization's success. And to achieve such, a good leader is needed.

Leadership is often defined as a process wherein an individual influences and encourages others to achieve the organizational objectives and directs the organization to become more coherent and cohesive. He is a person who can bring out change in others, always looks out for others before himself, and is proactive. To implement this concept in an effective and worthwhile manner, individuals need to acquire an understanding of the meaning and significance of leadership. They will put it into operation when they comprehend the various ideas and how these concepts will prove useful to them in carrying out their job duties well and achieving the desired goals.

The leaders aim to provide knowledge, support, and assistance to their subordinates in carrying out their job duties in a well-ordered and controlled manner and achieving the desired goals and objectives. When leaders perform their job duties or work with other individuals, they must teach the traits of morality and ethics, which lead to goodwill and well-being.

Consequently, leaders must be well aware of the ways essential to generating the desired outcomes and producing changes to an impressive extent. Leaders need to implement the potential for producing beneficial changes and normally convey to employees that they need to communicate well with others and cooperate with each other. Thus, working in co-operation will benefit them to a major extent because the individuals will be able to exchange viewpoints and perspectives, obtain help from others in solutions to problems, work in collaboration and integration with each other, and incur the feeling of job satisfaction. They do not have to consult their supervisors in terms of trivial issues.

Bask (2019) mentioned that leadership is vital in any organization. It involves defining the direction of a team and communicating it to people, motivating, inspiring, and empowering them to contribute to organizational success. It requires being strategically focused and applying behavioral techniques to build commitment and attain the best work from your people. The ingredients of effective leadership are complex and are widely agreed to depend on the specific leadership situation, considering the difficulty of tasks, the degree of a leader's authority, and the maturity and capabilities of subordinates. Leadership skills often take time to learn because they are multi-faceted, behavioral, and context-dependent.

Nowadays, there are already different leadership practices being adopted and implemented by leaders depending on their perceptions and techniques on how they would like to run or manage the organization. School administrators variedly implement these different leadership practices because they believe in their principles on how to make their organization succeed. This differentiates the ability

of a young leader from those who are old and already in the service.

To implement this concept in an effective and worthwhile manner, individuals need to acquire an understanding of the meaning and significance of leadership. When they understand the meaning and how this concept will be useful to them in carrying out their job duties well and achieving the desired goals, they will put it into operation. The leaders have the main objective of providing knowledge, support, and assistance to their subordinates in carrying out their job duties in a well-ordered and in a controlled manner to achieve the desired goals and objectives. When leaders perform their job duties or work with other individuals, they must teach the traits of morality and ethics, which lead to goodwill and well-being.

To implement this concept in an effective and worthwhile manner, individuals need to acquire an understanding of the meaning and significance of leadership. When they understand the meaning and how this concept will be useful to them in carrying out their job duties well and achieving the desired goals, they will put it into operation. The leaders have the main objective of providing knowledge, support, and assistance to their subordinates in carrying out their job duties in a well-ordered and in a controlled manner to achieve the desired goals and objectives. When leaders perform their job duties or work with others, they must teach morality and ethics, leading to goodwill and well-being.

It is through these concepts that the researcher was encouraged to conduct this study on the critical leadership roles of school administrators as a correlate of teachers' performance and school performance to identify the critical leadership roles being practiced by the school administrators to identify issues and concerns about the effective implementation of leadership roles and to identify if these leadership roles being adopted and practiced and implemented by the school administrators are contributory factors that can help in making the organization improve its performance..

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the instructional leadership of school administrators as correlate to teachers' performance which served as basis for an action plan during the school year 2024-2025. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the teachers on the instructional leadership of the school administrators roles in terms of the following?
 - 1.1. resource provider;
 - 1.2. instructional resource;
 - 1.3. communicator; and
 - 1.4. visible leader?
2. What is the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF of SY 2023-2024?
3. Is there any significant relationship between the instructional leadership roles of the school administrators and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF?
4. Based on the results of the study, what plan of action to be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design, according to Fox and Bayat (2019), who stated that descriptive research aims to investigate current issues or problems by collecting data that makes them elaborate on the situation completely.

Descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically. It can answer what, where, when and how questions, but not why questions. This practical approach, using a wide variety of research methods, allows for a systematic investigation of one or more variables.

Using descriptive research design, the researcher would be able to determine the school administrators' effectiveness regarding their critical roles in leading and managing their respective schools.

Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling. This was conducted in the selected schools of District I and II, Division of Antipolo City. The respondents to the study were teachers from the selected schools. Each instrument was administered to all the respondents. The respondents were given enough time to answer the research instrument. The scope of this study covered teachers from the selected schools of District I and District II, Division of Antipolo City.

Instrument

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire and descriptive questions that served as indicators in every variable. The survey questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part contained the demographic profile of the respondents. The second part contained the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the instructional leaders practices of the school administrators, and the third part contained the teacher's performance rating (IPCRF).

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the study was conducted. Upon approval of the school's division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the teacher-respondents from the selected public elementary schools of District I and District II, Division of Antipolo City, and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency, Percentage Distribution, Ranking This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

Pearson r Correlation. This was used to determine the significant relationship between the instructional leadership roles of the school administrators and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF.

Results and Discussion

This section provided the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers

Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers in terms of Resource Provider

Table 1. *Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers in terms of Resource Provider*

<i>The school administrator...</i>		<i>A. Resource Provider</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	helps find alternative teaching materials to provide additional practice with the skills.		3.33	Always	9
2.	keeps herself abreast of numerous changes and resources in education to provide opportunities for teachers to come up with instructional innovations.		3.54	Always	2
3.	updates teachers about the current research and practices through presentations or e-mails.		3.54	Always	3
4.	assists teachers in accessing and using professional resources to select appropriate strategies to improve student learning.		3.35	Always	7
5.	recommends, orders or authorizes purchase of instructional materials, supplies, equipment, and visual aids designed to meet student educational needs.		3.80	Always	1
6.	fosters team building and collaboration to improve instruction.		3.33	Always	10
7.	helps teachers share their best practices in teaching and classroom instruction.		3.45	Always	5
8.	ensures that teachers have materials necessary for the successful execution of their jobs.		3.34	Always	8
9.	employs a variety of communication and dissemination skills to share information and resources including school based- training to help improve the performance of teachers.		3.53	Always	4
10.	inspects instructional equipment to determine if repairs are needed.		3.36	Always	6
		Composite Mean	3.46	Always	

As discussed in Table 1, the respondents stated that the school administrators recommend, orders or authorizes purchase of instructional materials, supplies, equipment, and visual aids designed to meet student educational needs, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.80 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school administrators recommended, ordered, and authorized the purchase of instructional materials, supplies, equipment, and visual aids designed to meet student educational needs. Administrators played a crucial role in ensuring that classrooms were well-equipped with the necessary resources to support effective teaching and learning. School administrators meticulously assessed the needs of students and teachers to identify the most appropriate instructional materials and resources. They collaborated with teachers to understand the specific requirements of different subjects and grade levels, ensuring that the materials purchased were aligned with curriculum standards and instructional goals. According to Wolfe et al. (2023), effective instructional leadership in schools can be improved by addressing challenges in resource allocation and promoting a common understanding of instructional leadership.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators foster team building and collaboration to improve instruction which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.33 and least rank of 10. The findings indicated that school administrators fostered team building and collaboration to improve instruction, recognizing the pivotal role that a cohesive and collaborative staff plays in enhancing educational outcomes. Administrators implemented various strategies and initiatives to create an environment where teachers could work together effectively, share best practices, and support each other's professional growth. Administrators organized regular team-building activities and professional development workshops that encouraged collaboration among teachers. These activities were designed to build trust, improve communication, and foster a sense of community within the school. By creating opportunities for teachers to interact outside of their regular classroom duties, administrators helped to strengthen interpersonal relationships and promote a collaborative school culture. Zugelder (2021) stated that instructional leadership involves effective practices, aligned systems, data use, continuous improvement, and collaborative professional development for school personnel.

The composite mean of 3.46 implied that the instructional leadership practices of school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of being a resource provider is within high level. The findings indicated that the instructional leadership practices of school administrators, as perceived by teachers, were at a high level in terms of being resource providers. Teachers recognized and appreciated the administrators' proactive efforts in securing and distributing the necessary materials and support to enhance instructional quality and student learning outcomes. Administrators demonstrated their commitment to being effective resource providers by ensuring that classrooms were well-equipped with the latest instructional materials, technological tools, and educational resources. They actively sought funding opportunities, grants, and partnerships to expand the school's resources, thereby ensuring that teachers had access to high-quality materials that could enrich their teaching practices. A shared cluster construct of instructional leadership, including managing instructional programs and developing the school learning climate, shows modest relationships with teacher job satisfaction (Veletić & Olsen, 2021).

Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers in terms of Instructional Resource

Table 2. *Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers in terms of Instructional Resource*

<i>The school administrator...</i>	<i>B. Instructional Resource</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	conducts or participates in workshops, committees and conferences designed to promote the intellectual, social, and physical welfare of students.	3.34	Always	9
2.	evaluates the effectiveness of instructional programs of the school and applying remedial actions in areas requiring remediation.	3.49	Always	8
3.	facilitates professional learning among colleagues for the improvement of instruction.	3.77	Always	3
4.	works with colleagues to collect, analyze and disseminate data related to the quality of professional learning and its effect on teaching and student learning.	3.81	Always	1
5.	develops test, questionnaires and conduct procedures that measure the effectiveness of curricula and use these tools to determine whether program objectives are being met.	3.77	Always	4
6.	plans or conduct teacher training programs and conferences dealing with new classroom procedure, instructional materials and equipment and teaching aids.	3.78	Always	2
7.	observes work of teaching staff to evaluate performance and recommend changes that could strengthen teaching skills.	3.55	Always	7
8.	assists teachers in classroom organization and management.	3.55	Always	6
9.	helps teachers in interpreting test results to assess each pupil's abilities and performance.	3.64	Always	5
10.	shares knowledge and skills professionally and help identify powerful instructional strategies and effective elements of lesson plans for effective teaching and learning process.	3.49	Always	8
Composite Mean		3.62	Always	

As discussed in Table 2, the respondents stated that the school administrators work with colleagues to collect, analyze and disseminate data related to the quality of professional learning and its effect on teaching and student learning, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.81 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school administrators worked collaboratively with colleagues to collect, analyze, and disseminate data related to the quality of professional learning and its impact on teaching and student learning. This collaborative approach ensured that professional development initiatives were data-driven, targeted, and effective in enhancing educational outcomes. Administrators engaged in systematic data collection processes to gather comprehensive information on various aspects of professional learning. They utilized surveys, feedback forms, classroom observations, and performance metrics to assess the effectiveness of professional development programs. By involving teachers and other staff members in this process, administrators ensured that the data collected was reflective of the actual experiences and needs of the school community. Instructional leadership practices, positive teacher-administrator relationships, and ongoing professional development opportunities are crucial for promoting teacher professional growth and improving student learning outcomes (Kilag & Sasan, 2023).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators conduct or participates in workshops, committees and conferences designed to promote the intellectual, social, and physical welfare of students which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.34 and least rank of 9. The findings indicated that school administrators conducted or participated in workshops, committees, and conferences designed to promote the intellectual, social, and physical welfare of students. This active involvement underscored their commitment to fostering a holistic educational environment that supported all aspects of student development. Administrators organized and led workshops aimed at addressing various educational and developmental needs of students. These workshops covered a wide range of topics, including academic enrichment, social-emotional learning, physical health, and well-being. By providing teachers and staff with the latest research-based strategies and practical tools, administrators ensured that the entire school community was equipped to support student growth effectively. According to Munna (2021), instructional leadership in higher education improves learner achievement by establishing shared beliefs and fostering effective teaching and learning processes.

The composite mean of 3.62 implied that the instructional leadership practices of school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of being an instructional resource is within high level. The findings indicated that the instructional leadership practices of school

administrators, as perceived by teachers, were at a high level in terms of being an instructional resource. Teachers recognized and valued the administrators' efforts to provide substantial support, guidance, and resources that directly enhanced instructional practices and student learning outcomes. Administrators demonstrated their role as instructional resources by actively engaging in the development and dissemination of effective teaching strategies. They regularly organized and led professional development sessions, workshops, and training programs that introduced teachers to innovative instructional methods and best practices. By staying informed about the latest educational research and trends, administrators ensured that the content of these sessions was relevant and impactful. Head teacher leadership as an instructional resource for staff is often counter practiced, with pitfalls in administrative tasks and failure to monitor and supervise team performance (Poudel & Subedi, 2022).

Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers in terms of Communicator

Table 3. *Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers in terms of Communicator*

<i>The school administrator...</i>	<i>C. Communicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. models effective skills in listening, presenting ideas, leading discussions, clarifying, and identifying the needs of self and others in order to advance shared goals and professional learning.		3.54	Always	3
2. provides constructive feedback to colleagues to strengthen teaching practice and improve student learning.		3.82	Always	1
3. holds meetings to discuss instructional concerns of the school.		3.39	Always	6
4. organizes information and ideas to be discussed during meetings.		3.53	Always	4
5. creates a climate of trust and critical reflection to engage colleagues in challenging conversations about student learning and solutions to identified issues.		3.34	Always	8
6. motivates teachers to work cooperatively to promote changes in instructional practices to improve student learning.		3.45	Always	5
7. collaborates with teachers in the design and formulation of instructional objectives to improve educational practice and student learning.		3.33	Always	9
8. leads formal and informal group discussions.		3.80	Always	2
9. serves as a team leader to harness the skills, expertise, and knowledge of colleagues to address curricular expectations and student learning needs.		3.35	Always	7
10. shows collegiality with teachers, non-teaching staff, and parents.		3.54	Always	3
	Composite Mean	3.51	Always	

As discussed in Table 3, the respondents stated that the school administrators provide constructive feedback to colleagues to strengthen teaching practice and improve student learning, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.82 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school administrators provided constructive feedback to colleagues to strengthen teaching practice and improve student learning. Teachers valued this aspect of administrators' instructional leadership, recognizing the positive impact of timely and specific feedback on their professional development and instructional effectiveness. Administrators employed a variety of methods to deliver constructive feedback, ensuring it was both supportive and actionable. Through regular classroom observations, they gathered detailed insights into teaching practices and student engagement. Following these observations, administrators conducted one-on-one meetings with teachers, offering specific feedback that highlighted strengths and identified areas for improvement. This personalized approach allowed teachers to reflect on their practices and implement targeted strategies to enhance their instruction. According to Parveen et al. (2023), instructional leadership practices positively impact students' academic achievement through motivation, teacher competency, self-efficacy, and effective classroom management.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators collaborate with teachers in the design and formulation of instructional objectives to improve educational practice and student learning which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.33 and least rank of 9. The findings indicated that school administrators collaborated closely with teachers in the design and formulation of instructional objectives to improve educational practice and student learning. This collaborative approach was highly valued by teachers, who appreciated the administrators' active involvement and support in shaping the educational goals and strategies used in their classrooms.

Administrators engaged teachers in regular planning meetings and workshops focused on developing clear, measurable, and achievable instructional objectives. These sessions provided a platform for teachers to share their insights and experiences, ensuring that the objectives were well-informed by classroom realities and aligned with the curriculum standards. By involving teachers in this process, administrators fostered a sense of ownership and commitment among the staff, which was crucial for the successful implementation of the objectives. Shaked (2020) stated that higher education leaders show little instructional leadership, mainly due to faculty autonomy, low teaching quality priorities, and the academic teaching style.

The composite mean of 3.51 implied that the instructional leadership practices of school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of being a communicator is within high level. The findings indicated that the instructional leadership practices of school administrators, as perceived by teachers, were at a high level in terms of being communicators. Teachers acknowledged and appreciated

the administrators' ability to effectively communicate important information, foster open dialogue, and create a transparent and collaborative school environment. Administrators demonstrated their strong communication skills through regular and clear dissemination of information. They ensured that teachers were well-informed about school policies, curriculum changes, professional development opportunities, and other important updates. This consistent flow of information helped teachers stay aligned with the school's goals and expectations, reducing uncertainties and fostering a cohesive educational community. Organizational management functions support four main aspects of instructional leadership: developing a positive learning climate, improving teaching quality, realizing the school instructional vision, and enabling instructional leadership (Widtayakornbundit & Phinaitrup, 2020).

Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers in terms of Visible Leader

Table 4. *Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers in terms of Visible Leader*

<i>The school administrator...</i>	<i>D. Visible Leader</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. participates in in-service activities related to his/her duties.		3.54	Always	6
2. arrives punctually to work, programs and meetings.		3.33	Always	9
3. conducts meetings with the teachers to share and discuss matters related to instructional concerns.		3.59	Always	5
4. participates in joint parent-teacher meetings as agreed upon with the classroom/subject teacher.		3.63	Always	4
5. provides accessibility with teachers to discuss matters affecting curriculum and instruction.		3.50	Always	7
6. attends and/or participates in any activity organized by the pupils or teachers.		3.66	Always	3
7. gives positive feedback to teachers regarding their behavior and performance.		3.32	Always	10
8. mediates and interacts in a parent conference when appropriate, especially if it involves a complaint about teachers.		3.79	Always	1
9. acknowledges quality of output in teachers' and pupils' activities such as convocations, organizational meetings, and others.		3.43	Always	8
10. makes himself/herself available for meetings and/or appointments with pupils, teachers, parents, and the stakeholders.		3.66	Always	2
	Composite Mean	3.55	Always	

As discussed in Table 4, the respondents stated that the school administrators mediate and interacts in a parent conference when appropriate, especially if it involves a complaint about teachers, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.79 and the highest rank of 1. The school administrators mediated and interacted in parent conferences when appropriate, particularly when they involved complaints about teachers. Administrators played a crucial role in facilitating constructive dialogue between parents and teachers, aiming to address concerns effectively while maintaining a supportive and professional atmosphere. Administrators approached parent conferences with a focus on understanding and resolving issues. They listened attentively to parents' concerns, ensuring that they fully grasped the nature of the complaint and the underlying issues. This active listening helped administrators gather relevant information and insights, enabling them to assess the situation comprehensively. According to Hallinger et al. (2020), instructional leadership has become a global expectation for school principals, with a growing knowledge base and geographic scope, and is now integrated with complementary leadership approaches.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators give positive feedback to teachers regarding their behavior and performance which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.32 and least rank of 10. The school administrators provided positive feedback to teachers regarding their behavior and performance, fostering a supportive and motivational work environment. This practice was highly valued by teachers, as it acknowledged their efforts and contributions while reinforcing desired behaviors and instructional practices. Administrators delivered positive feedback in various forms and contexts. They recognized and praised teachers during staff meetings, highlighting specific instances of exemplary teaching, classroom management, or student engagement. This public acknowledgment not only boosted morale but also served as a model for other teachers to emulate successful practices. Mala et al. (2020) stated that instructional leadership effectively improves student learning activity and learning outcomes.

The composite mean of 3.55 implied that the instructional leadership practices of school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of being a visible leader is within high level. The findings indicated that the instructional leadership practices of school administrators, as perceived by teachers, were at a high level in terms of being visible leaders.

Teachers recognized and appreciated the administrators' active presence and engagement throughout the school community, which contributed to a positive and supportive educational environment. Administrators demonstrated their visibility as leaders by actively participating in various school activities and events. They regularly attended faculty meetings, parent-teacher conferences, and school assemblies, demonstrating their commitment to being accessible and involved in the daily life of the school. This visible presence helped administrators establish rapport with teachers, students, and parents, fostering trust and open communication. Chikwanda et al. (2020) stated that instructional leadership style positively influences the creation of conducive teaching and learning environments in colleges of education.

Teacher’s performance based on IPCRF

Table 5. *Teacher’s performance based on IPCRF*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
4.1 - 5.00 (Outstanding)	96	63.58	1
3.1 – 4.00 (Very Satisfactory)	55	36.42	2
Total	151	100.00	
Mean Grade	4.41 (Outstanding)		
Standard Deviation	0.05 (Compressed)		

As given in Table 5, majority of 151 teacher-respondents or 63.58% at rank 1 have an Outstanding IPCRF performances. The table presented the results of the Teacher Performance Evaluation for the academic year 2023-2024, as assessed through the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). Teacher performance was categorized into two main ranges based on their evaluation scores. The highest category, ranging from 4.1 to 5.00, denoted "Outstanding" performance, with 96 teachers, accounting for 63.58% of the total evaluated, achieving scores within this range. The second category, spanning from 3.1 to 4.00, signified "Very Satisfactory" performance, with 55 teachers, comprising 36.42% of the total, falling into this range. The table illustrated the frequency and percentage of teachers in each category, emphasizing the predominant presence of outstanding and very satisfactory performances among the evaluated teachers. Furthermore, it ranked the performance categories based on the number of teachers, highlighting the outstanding category as the most frequently attained. The evaluation had a mean grade of 4.41, reflecting an overall high level of performance, while the low standard deviation of 0.05 indicated consistency in evaluation scores around this mean. These findings collectively provided a clear and structured overview of teacher performance outcomes, underscoring that the majority of teachers had achieved commendable ratings based on their IPCRF assessments for the specified academic period.

According to Llovio et al. (2023), teacher performance in educational contexts is influenced by their role in management, leadership, competitiveness, and academic training, with professional training and skills being crucial for achieving educational quality.

Relationship between the Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by The Teachers and the Teacher’s performance based on IPCRF

Table 6. *Relationship between the Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers and the Teacher’s performance based on IPCRF*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Instructional Leadership Practices and Teacher’s performance	0.79	0.00872	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

As written in Table 6, the correlation analysis between Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators, as perceived by teachers, and Teacher's performance based on the IPCRF revealed a significant result. The r-value of 0.79 indicated a strong positive correlation between these variables, suggesting that as instructional leadership practices improved, teacher performance, as evaluated through the IPCRF, also improved correspondingly. The p-value of 0.00872 indicated that this correlation was statistically significant at a conventional significance level. With the p-value being less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho) was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis, confirming a significant relationship between instructional leadership practices and teacher performance.

This finding implied that effective instructional leadership, as perceived by teachers, played a crucial role in enhancing teacher performance. When school administrators demonstrated strong instructional leadership practices—such as providing clear direction, supporting professional development, fostering a positive school culture, and facilitating effective teaching and learning environments—teachers were more likely to perform well according to the IPCRF evaluations. This correlation underscored the importance of supportive and effective leadership in educational settings, as it directly influenced teacher effectiveness and overall school performance metrics. Therefore, investing in enhancing instructional leadership skills among school administrators could lead to improved teacher performance and, consequently, better educational outcomes for students.

Action Plan

Table 7. *Proposed Action Plan*

<i>Program</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>2025-2026</i>
Professional Development Program	Enhance leadership skills (communication, data-driven decision-making)	Quarterly workshops throughout the year
Data Utilization Initiative	Regular assessment of student performance and teacher evaluations	Monthly data review sessions
Collaborative Leadership Forums	Foster collaboration on instructional strategies and school improvement	Quarterly meetings
Parent and Community Engagement Program	Increase involvement in school activities and support initiatives	Quarterly community events; bi-annual parent-teacher conferences
Inclusive School Environment Initiative	Implement policies promoting inclusivity and equity	Ongoing review and implementation; annual assessment

Table 7 outlined a comprehensive action plan aimed at enhancing instructional leadership and improving overall school effectiveness through targeted programs and initiatives.

The Professional Development Program was designed to bolster leadership skills among school administrators, focusing on communication and data-driven decision-making. It included quarterly workshops throughout the year, led by the Human Resources Department, ensuring leaders were equipped with necessary competencies to guide and support their teams effectively.

The Data Utilization Initiative underscored the importance of regularly assessing student performance and teacher evaluations. It involved monthly data review sessions facilitated by the Academic Affairs Department, fostering a culture of continuous improvement by leveraging data insights to inform instructional strategies and interventions.

The Collaborative Leadership Forums provided a structured platform for fostering collaboration among staff members on instructional strategies and school improvement initiatives. These bi-monthly meetings, led by the School Leadership Team, encouraged the sharing of best practices, innovative ideas, and collective problem-solving to enhance teaching effectiveness and student outcomes.

The Parent and Community Engagement Program focused on increasing involvement in school activities and garnering support for educational initiatives. Through quarterly community events and bi-annual parent-teacher conferences organized by the Community Relations Coordinator, this program aimed to strengthen partnerships with parents and community stakeholders, fostering a sense of shared responsibility for student success.

Lastly, the Inclusive School Environment Initiative aimed to implement policies promoting inclusivity and equity within the school community. The Diversity and Inclusion Committee regularly reviewed, implemented, and assessed policies to ensure a supportive and respectful environment for all students, staff, and families.

These action plans were strategically designed to address recommendations for enhancing instructional leadership practices. By focusing on professional development, data utilization, collaborative forums, parent and community engagement, and inclusivity, the school aimed to cultivate a cohesive and supportive environment conducive to academic success and holistic student development.

Instructional leaders incorporate a social justice perspective into school mission, program management, and climate development to address outcomes, belongingness, and discipline inequities (Shaked, 2023).

Conclusions

Several key conclusions were drawn based on the comprehensive analysis of the Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as perceived by teachers. As resource providers, school administrators play a crucial role in recommending, ordering, and authorizing the purchase of instructional materials, supplies, equipment, and visual aids necessary to meet students' educational needs. Administrators meticulously assessed the needs of both students and teachers, ensuring that classrooms were well-equipped with resources aligned with curriculum standards and instructional goals. This proactive approach enhanced the quality of instruction and supported effective teaching and learning throughout the school.

Administrators, as instructional resources, fostered a culture of collaboration by working closely with colleagues to collect, analyze, and disseminate data related to the impact of professional learning on teaching and student outcomes. This collaborative, data-driven approach ensured that professional development initiatives were targeted and effective, contributing to continuous improvement in educational practices. Administrators also took the lead in organizing workshops, committees, and conferences aimed at promoting the intellectual, social, and physical welfare of students, demonstrating a commitment to holistic educational support.

Also, administrators excelled as communicators by delivering constructive feedback and collaborating with teachers to design instructional objectives that enhanced educational practices and student learning. They facilitated regular planning meetings and workshops where teachers could contribute their insights and experiences, fostering a collaborative environment conducive to professional growth and development. Administrators' effective communication of policies, curriculum changes, and professional development opportunities kept teachers informed and aligned with school goals, promoting a cohesive and supportive school culture.

Moreover, administrators demonstrated their visibility as leaders by mediating parent conferences and providing positive feedback to teachers. They actively engaged in school events, assemblies, and community activities, fostering trust and communication within the educational community. Their visible presence and supportive interactions with stakeholders reinforced a sense of unity and shared responsibility for student success. The correlation analysis between Instructional Leadership Practices and Teacher Performance revealed a strong positive relationship. Effective leadership practices significantly enhanced teacher performance, underscoring the critical role of supportive and proactive leadership in achieving positive educational outcomes.

In conclusion, these findings underscore the profound impact of instructional leadership practices on school effectiveness and teacher performance. Investments in enhancing leadership skills among administrators are crucial for sustaining instructional quality, fostering a collaborative school environment, and ultimately improving educational outcomes for students. It is imperative that future efforts continue to focus on the continuous development and support of effective leadership practices to empower educators and promote excellence in teaching and learning across all educational settings.

Several key recommendations emerge based on the conclusions drawn from the analysis of instructional leadership practices and their impact on school effectiveness and teacher performance. Firstly, continuous professional development programs should be implemented for school administrators, focusing on enhancing leadership skills such as effective communication, data-driven decision-making, and the cultivation of a collaborative school culture. These initiatives are crucial in equipping administrators to support and inspire their teaching staff effectively. Secondly, there is a need to strengthen data utilization in decision-making processes. Administrators should regularly assess student performance data, teacher evaluations, and stakeholder feedback to identify improvement areas and strategically allocate resources to enhance instructional quality.

Furthermore, the promotion of collaborative leadership practices is of utmost importance. Establishing regular forums for administrators and teachers to jointly discuss instructional strategies, curriculum development, and school improvement initiatives not only enhances transparency but also leverages the collective expertise of the school community. This collaborative approach is a key factor in improving school effectiveness and teacher performance.

Lastly, creating a supportive and inclusive school environment is crucial. Administrators can nurture a safe and supportive learning environment by prioritizing policies and practices that promote inclusivity, equity, and respect among students, staff, and families. These recommendations aim to empower school administrators with the tools and strategies to cultivate effective instructional leadership practices. Administrators can strengthen their leadership capacity by focusing on professional development, data-driven decision-making, collaboration, community engagement, and inclusive school environments, ultimately enhancing educational outcomes for all students.

References

- Akbaba-Altun, S. (2020). Information technology classrooms and elementary school principals' roles: Turkish exp.
- Anderson, J. B. (2020). Principals' role and public primary schools' effectiveness in four Latin American cities. *The Elementary School Journal*, 109(1), 36-60.
- Barnett, D. (2019). School leadership preparation programs: Are they preparing tomorrow's leaders? *Education*, 125(1), 121 -129.
- Barth, R. S. (2020). Teacher leader. *Phi Delta Kappan* 82, (4) 443-49.
- Bass, R. K. (2020). Leadership Roles, Guidelines and Directives. *Evaluation practice*, 15(3), 283-290.
- Bradshaw, L. K. (2020). The changing role of principals in school partnerships. *NASSP Bulletin*, 84,86-96.
- Chikwanda, R., Masaiti, G., & Banda, D. (2020). Instructional Leadership Style and Its Influence on Creation of Conducive Teaching and Learning Environment in Colleges of Education in Zambia.. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*. <https://doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0707011>.
- Cisler, A., & Bruce, M. A. (2020). Principals: What are their roles and responsibilities? *Journal of School Counseling*, 11(10), n10.
- Cosner, S. (2020). Supporting the initiation and early development of evidence-based grade-level collaboration in urban elementary schools: Key roles and strategies of principals and literacy coordinators. *Urban Education*, 46(4), 786-827.
- Day, L., et.al., (2020). *The strategies employed by principals which resulted in school improvement*. Albany: State University of New York Press.
- Dilworth, M. E., & Thomas, I. K. (2020). *PK-12 Educational Leadership and Administration White Paper*. Washington, DC: American Association of Curriculum and Teacher Education.
- Evans, P. (2020). The Effective Leadership Roles: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas, 79(2), 83-87.
- Fry, B., & Gray, C. (2019). Preparing highly qualified school leaders. Illinois benchmarking report executive summary. Southern Regional Board. Retrieved,May,2019,from<http://www.ibhe.state.il.us/SchoolLeaderspeeting1105/IllinoisExecSummary.pdf>.
- Gardiner, M. E., & Enomoto, E. K. (2019). Urban school principals and their role as multicultural leaders. *Urban Education*, 41(6), 560- 584.
- Grosso de Leon, A. (2019). The school leadership crisis: Have school principals been left behind? *The Carnegie Reporter*. 4(1). Retrieved November 17,2019, from <http://www.carnegie.org/reporter/13/crisis/index.html>.
- Hallinger, P., Gümüş, S., & Bellibaş, M. (2020). 'Are principals instructional leaders yet?' A science map of the knowledge base on instructional leadership, 1940–2018. *Scientometrics*, 122, 1629 - 1650. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03360-5>.
- Hoerr, T. R. (2020). Principal as parachute. *Educational Leadership* 90-91.
- Hopper, K. (2020) "Elementary Principal Perception on Key Leadership Responsibilities Associated with Increased Student Achievement". Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.

- Hunvitz, S. (2020, August 4). The super bowl. *Education Life*, p. 15.
- Kalai, H. (2019). A Study of Educational management Practices in Secondary Schools and their Implications for In-Service Training of Head teachers: A Survey of Kitui and Machakos Districts, Kenya” [Electronic version]. *Educational Researcher* 33(8), 3-15.
- Kalra, J. (2020) Exploration of the competencies required by senior secondary school principals for managing their school efficiently. <http://www.ncela.gwu.edu~ncbepubs/report.htm#Contents>.
- Kathleen, J. (1979). *Administrative Leadership*, No. 19, 121-129.
- Kelly, E. (Ed.). (2020). *Transactional and Transformational Leadership*: Cambridge University Press.
- Kilag, O., & Sasan, J. (2023). Unpacking the Role of Instructional Leadership in Teacher Professional Development. *Advanced Qualitative Research*. <https://doi.org/10.31098/aqr.v1i1.1380>.
- Kindred, L. W. (2020). What is the principal's responsibility for supervision? *The bulletin of the National Association of Secondary School Principals*, 35(178), 15-18.
- Kivipold M., & Vadi, C.M. (2020). Educational policy actions by the ministry of national education in the times of COVID-19. *Kastamonu Education Journal*, 28(3), 1124-1129. doi: 10.24106/kefdergi.722280.
- Kwan, P. (2021). Examining the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relation between responsibilities and career aspiration of vice-principals. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 50(5-6), 349-361.
- Llovio, D., Holguin, R., Rodriguez, D., Fatima, V., & Barzola, R. (2023). Teacher performance: a perception from the theory. *Universidad Ciencia y Tecnología*. <https://doi.org/10.47460/uct.v27i118.689>.
- Loeb, et.al., (2019). *Reframing organizations: What school leadership comprises?* (31d ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Mala, Y., Roesminingsih, E., & Riyanto, Y. (2021). The effect of instructional leadership on student’s active and learning outcomes. *Jurnal Pembangunan Pendidikan: Fondasi dan Aplikasi*. <https://doi.org/10.21831/JPPFA.V9I1.40316>.
- Mishra, S. K., & Yadav, B. (2020). Role ability among the middle-class principals (Khargone (MP) India). *International Journal of Education*, 5(1), 156.
- Mullen, C. A., & Hutinger, J. L. (2019). The principal's role in fostering collaborative learning communities through faculty study group development. *Theory into practice*, 47(4), 276-285.
- Munna, A. (2021). Instructional Leadership and Role of Module Leaders. *International Journal of Educational Reform*, 32, 38 - 54. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10567879211042321>.
- Orr, M., (2020). *School leadership study developing successful principals .How preparation influences school leaders and their school improvement: Comparing exemplary and conventionally prepared principals*. Stanford University School of Education. Retrieved, from <http://seli.stanford.edu/research~doc~t.pdf>.
- Parveen, N., Rubab, U., Rahman, F., & Yousuf, M. (2023). Instructional Leadership Practices and Students' Academic Achievement. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. <https://doi.org/10.55737/qjssh.183216860>.
- Pasternak, I., Williams, J., & Anderson, J. (2020). The principal's role in promoting teachers' extra-role behaviors: Some insights from road-safety education. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 12(4), 420-439.
- Plecki, D. (Ed.). (2019). *Lifting every voice. Pedagogy and politics of bilingualism*. Cambridge, MA. Harvard Education Publishing Group.
- Poudel, R., & Subedi, R. (2022). Exploring Head Teacher Leadership as Instructional Resource for Staff: Stories from a School of South Asia. *European Journal of Educational Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ejetechn.2022.2>.
- Shaked, H. (2020). Instructional leadership in higher education: The case of Israel. *Higher Education Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.12274>.
- Shaked, H. (2023). How instructional leaders promote social justice. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17411432231168227>.
- Southern Regional Education Board. (2019). *Schools need good leaders now: State progress in creating a learning-centered school leadership system*. Retrieved, from <http://www.sreb.org/main/Goals/PublicationO7V48 - School-leadership.pdf>.
- Spillane, J. P., & Lee, L. C. (2020). Novice school principals’ sense of ultimate responsibility: Problems of practice in transitioning to the principal’s office. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 50(3), 431-465.
- Tirozzi, G. (2021) *The artistry of leadership: The evolving role of the secondary school principal*. *Phi Delta Kappan* 42(6), 434-439.

Veletić, J., & Olsen, R. (2021). Developing a shared cluster construct of instructional leadership in TALIS. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 68, 100942. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2020.100942>.

Wegenke, G. L. (2019). Principal's role in school restructuring in the Des Moines public schools. *Education and Urban Society*, 32(4), 519-534.

White-Smith, K. A., & White, M. A. (2019). High school reform implementation: Principals' perceptions on their leadership role. *Urban Education*, 44(3), 259-279.

Widtayakornbundit, S., & Phinaitrup, B. (2020). MEDIATING EFFECTS OF RELATIONSHIP QUALITY ON THE CORRELATIONS BETWEEN INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP AND LOYALTY. , 8, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.22452/MOJEM.VOL8NO2.1>.

Wolfe, Z., Knudsen, K., & Mahaffey, A. (2023). Distribution of Instructional Leadership Roles within a School Organization. *Excelsior: Leadership in Teaching and Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.14305/jn.19440413.2023.15.1.02>.

Yukl, R. (2019) Influential leadership of school principals. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 44(2), 141-160.

Zugelder, B. (2021). Instructional Leadership. *Advances in Educational Marketing, Administration, and Leadership*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-6500-1.CH002>.

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